

(Bruce Riley, 2014)

Listening to the city from within

Opportunities for collaboration

Core Members

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1. Introduction

AI+ Algorithm Inventory

This collaboration aims to critically explore, analyze, and reflect the role of algorithms and the datafication of the city. Through this, we open opportunities and pathways to develop and design mechanisms for collaborative and public deliberation on data collection and use.

- **Uncertainties in data**
To understand all the sources of uncertainty.
To identify people's mental models in the creation of data collection, find the potential uncertainties and the gaps within data collection, and find compelling approaches that enrich our perceptions of the city realm.
- **Co-creation and reciprocal**
To propose a framework that concretely triggers a community of practice in the work of datafication. Collective decisions and dissemination, which included the design of strategies to increase data awareness.
- **Sensory methodologies**
To propose a sensorial experience that can be shown in arts and culture spaces in which data is repurposed from an inventory perspective to a dialogue on the environment, the city, and personal experience.

Certainty taxonomy

Certainty tags in TEI allow to annotate missing or incorrect information, specify your confidence on a modification, and collaborate with other people's work through nested annotations. Choose what different sources of uncertainty you will use to describe your annotations and their color and icon scheme.

Category name

Example text with current scheme

× in **some ignorance** sed,urna mauris, dapibus **some**
credibility dapibusmetus. Integer urna **some**
imprecision metus. Integer urna mauris,mauris,
× dapibus in lacus sed, **some incompleteness** sed,
dictum porttitor metus.

2. Aims and Objectives

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Overview of the co-creation approach with paper-based materials and digital tools during workshop interactions.

2. Aims and Objectives

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- Framing through listening -

- **Design and scientific reflection** of the cross-sectoral, cross-organizational, co-work setting.
- **Community Participation.** Interaction and exchange to encourage social interaction and discussions between participants on their on-site experience;
- **Awareness.** Collective decisions and dissemination, which included the design of strategies to increase data awareness.

(Antony Gormley, 2011)

(Bruce Riley, 2014)

2. Aims and Objectives

AI+ Algorithm Inventory

Expanding our active experience with data

-*Urban Auscultation* is meant to acknowledge and center the symbiotic connections between our bodies and our cities, and how these connections are inherently unpredictable, fluid, and dynamic-

The sensorial as visualization approach

Opportunity for collaboration

- Identify people's mental models in data collection and the gaps in compelling an experience on the city.
- A sensorial experience that repurposes data from an inventory perspective to a dialogue on environment, the city, and personal experience.
- A novel approach in the design of algorithms processes, based on new understandings, scenarios, uncertainty, and principles of care in data collection
- To develop and design mechanisms for collaborative and public deliberation on data collection and use.

3. Opportunities and Engagements

AI+
Algorithm
Inventarium

Environment: Symbiotic Connections

While algorithms have been central to climate modelling - as well to how mitigation and adaptation strategies are evaluated - relatively little attention to date has been directed towards the political implications of knowing, acting on and governing climate change through an algorithm.

Achille Mbembe contends that **ideas of natural selection are coded into computational technologies, such as algorithms**, but specifically applications of genetic and evolutionary algorithms.

"If humans are necessarily embodied and inherently exist in a web of relations, as tech becomes a medium that envisages "frictionless" interaction, it treats the person as a disembodied soul and cuts away the web of relation essential for existence."

– Abeba Birhane

Algorithms capture more than just people's bodies. They also capture and trace our limits of imagination, and offer technological fixes for a wide range of social problems.

Through a series of online and physical interactions, we explore algorithms, its agency and the inherently biological bonds embedded in them. Moreover, this also allows us to explore the auscultation aspect, listening from within our urban environment.

- A multi sensorial approach to reveal data effects on biodiversity and climate
- What can sound tell us about how the world is changing and our future?
- In what ways can ecological change be represented to instigate meaningful change?

3. Example/Biodiversity

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image:ELAINE GAN, 2017

Our approach:

We want the infrastructure, steps, histories, alongside the smells and sound to guide our discussions.

From this perspective, urban spaces are not stable inert information, and they are activated and actualized by practices of those across them, our bodies turn in generative grammar put in place by walking.

We aim to work together on the elaboration of related scientific papers to discuss our results in a scientifically relevant way focused on participatory methods, sustainability transition, biodiversity, art-driven innovation, and technology.

Seeing the urban space as a linguistic system, provides functionalism to space, however, pedestrians can also redefine, reinvent, and deny its rules.

*Example:
A visual exploration for biodiversity data. It draws on tens of thousands of observations from citizen science platform. It is an experiment in how biodiversity data can support rich, engaging representations of living landscapes; and in particular how data points can be "re-integrated" to emphasise coexistence and community.*

3. Example/Biodiversity

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Image: Local Kin, Mitchell Whitelaw,

Photos: Oliver Hangl, 2021

4. Upcoming work

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- Upcoming Work -

- **Encouraging multisensory perspectives** can support new configurations that repurpose databases and algorithms from a 'fixed' inventory perspective to 'fluid' ongoing dialogues on biodiversity, the city, and personal narratives.
- **Participations**
 - European Council of Landscape Architecture Schools 2021 ([ECLAS](#))
 - Ars Electronica Festival 2021 ([AE2021](#))
 - ***Taking a memory out for a walk: data, archives, and the city***
 - ***An algorithmic soundwalk*** narrates the past and present ongoing histories of -places as data settings- present in language, space, environment and sound in Vienna.

(Antony Gormley, 2011)

(Bruce Riley, 2014)

5. Key for Collaboration

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This collaboration requires access to raw data and a clear understanding of the formats used conventionally in the projects. This is to analyze the taxonomies, uncertainties, patterns, occurrences, and categorizations.